

Studies on Transition Metal Complexes of Some Cyanoethylated Sulphonamides

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A number of N^1 -(β -cyanoethyl)-heterocyclic sulphonamides were prepared. They also act as chelating agents. The complexes of such sulphonamides with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) chlorides have been synthesised and studied. Physico-chemical measurements reveal that metal ligand ratio is 1 : 1 and all complexes are paramagnetic.

THE applicability of sulphonamides is well documented. Their cyanoethylation enhances the effectiveness as drug¹⁻⁴. They not only show antibacterial property but also have a tendency to form complexes with metal ions. Shukla *et al.*⁵ have reported the chelating ability of cyanoethylated sulphonamides with Hg(II) chloride. We have extended the present study on the interaction of transition metals with a variety of cyanoethylated sulphonamides.

Experimental

The ligands were synthesised according to the method described earlier⁶. Their analytical data are stated in Table 1 and 3.

(a) Preparation of N^1 -(β -cyanoethyl)-2-pyridyl sulphanilamide :

A mixture of N^1 -2-pyridyl sulphanilamide (5 g), 'Triton B' (0.5 g) and dioxane (20 ml) was stirred and to this was added freshly distilled acrylonitrile (2.0 g) dropwise at 30-35° for 48 hours at room temperature. At the end of this period the reaction

mixture was acidified, to yield the solid product, which was crystallised in colourless needles, m.p. 165° (lit.164°), yield : 73%. Analysis : Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}N_4O_2S$: C, 55.63% ; N, 18.55%. Found : C, 55.34% ; N, 18.20%.

(b) Preparation of complexes :

The complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II)⁷ chlorides were prepared by refluxing an ethanolic solution of ligands with metal chlorides in equal ratio. To the refluxing mixture an ethanolic solution of sodium hydroxide was added till pH was maintained at ~8. The refluxing was further continued for 3 hrs. The product thus obtained, was filtered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried in vacuum.

The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in nitrobenzene and dimethylformamide.

(c) Analysis :

The percentage of metal and chlorine contents were estimated gravimetrically. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the coordination compounds

TABLE 1— N^1 -(β -CYANOETHYL)-2-HETEROCYCLIC SULPHANILAMIDES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	Molecular formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %	
						Calcd.	Found
1.	Pyridyl	H	$C_{14}H_{14}N_4O_2S$	165	73.00	18.55	18.20
2.	β -cyanoethyl	H	$C_{12}H_{14}N_4O_2S$	148-144	84.60	20.15	20.00
3.	Thiazolyl	H	$C_{13}H_{12}N_4O_2S_2$	120-121	69.00	18.18	17.80
4.	Pyrimidyl	H	$C_{13}H_{12}N_4O_2S$	211-212	65.00	23.11	22.92
5.	4-methylpyrimidyl	H	$C_{14}H_{14}N_4O_2S$	205-206	66.60	22.08	21.82
6.	4,6-dimethylpyrimidyl	H	$C_{15}H_{17}N_4O_2S$	172	70.60	21.14	20.98

The analysis of carbon and hydrogen are with in the range of $\pm 0.5\%$.

were determined by well known combustion method. Results are listed in Table 2.

(d) *Physical measurements :*

I.R. spectra of coordination compounds were recorded with Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer model 137E. The electronic spectra of the complexes (in dimethylformamide 300-700 $m\mu$) were recorded on Beckman DU-2 (manual) spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurements

on solid complexes were made by Gouy method using mercury(II) tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as calibrating agents.

Conductivity measurements were carried out at 25° with Phillips magic eye, type P.R. 1500. The conductivity bridge had a cell constant of 0.183. The complexes at a final concentration of 1 μ M were dissolved in nitrobenzene for such measurements. The results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS AND PHYSICAL MEASUREMENTS

Sl. No.	Complex	M%	C%	H%	N%	Cl%	Conductance in mhos $\times 10^{-5}$	Magnetic moments
		Calcd. Found	Calcd. Found	Calcd. Found	Calcd. Found	Calcd. Found		
I	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-pyridyl sulphanyl amide] Copper II	14.56	38.50	3.20	12.83	16.25	0.96	1.82 B.M.
		14.00	38.10	3.00	12.52	16.01		
II	Dichloro[N ¹ , N ^{1'} -bis-(β - cyano-ethyl) sulphanyl amide] Copper II	15.41	34.92	3.39	13.58	17.19	1.05	1.9 B.M.
		15.00	34.52	3.00	13.02	17.00		
III	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-thiazolyl sulphanyl amide] Copper II	14.36	32.56	2.71	12.66	16.03	1.18	1.9 B.M.
		14.00	32.03	2.34	12.31	15.89		
IV	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-pyrimidyl sulphanyl amide] Copper II	14.53	35.67	2.97	16.01	16.21	0.92	1.86 B.M.
		14.08	35.12	2.62	15.90	16.00		
V	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-(4-methyl pyrimidyl) sulphanyl amide] Copper II	14.08	37.21	3.32	15.51	15.70	1.24	1.84 B.M.
		13.59	37.00	3.01	15.02	15.12		
VI	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-(4,6 dimethyl pyrimidyl) sulphanyl amide] Copper II	13.66	38.68	3.65	15.04	15.23	1.10	1.78 B.M.
		13.12	38.12	3.23	14.69	15.00		
VII	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-pyridyl sulphanyl amide] Nickel II	13.60	38.92	3.24	12.97	16.43	1.02	3.48 B.M.
		13.10	38.50	3.01	12.43	16.00		
VIII	Dichloro[N ¹ , N ^{1'} -bis-(β -cyano- ethyl) sulphanyl amide] Nickel II	14.41	35.34	3.43	13.74	17.40	0.82	3.50 B.M.
		14.00	35.00	3.12	13.43	17.32		
IX	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-thiazolyl sulphanyl amide] Nickel II	13.42	32.91	2.75	12.80	16.21	0.92	3.52 B.M.
		12.89	32.90	2.45	12.53	16.00		
X	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-pyrimidyl sulphanyl amide] Nickel II	13.57	36.06	3.00	16.18	16.39	1.12	3.6 B.M.
		13.31	35.82	2.89	16.00	16.20		
XI	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-(4-methyl pyrimidyl) sulphanyl amide] Nickel II	13.14	37.61	3.35	15.68	15.88	1.34	3.58 B.M.
		12.73	37.18	2.89	15.12	15.24		
XII	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-(4,6-dimethyl pyrimidyl) sulphanyl amide] Nickel II	12.75	39.07	3.69	15.19	15.39	1.12	3.62 B.M.
		12.43	38.68	3.21	15.00	15.01		
XIII	Dichloro [N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-pyridyl sulphanyl amide] Cobalt II	13.65	38.90	3.24	12.97	16.42	1.08	4.4 B.M.
		13.20	38.54	3.00	12.52	16.12		
XIV	Dichloro[N ¹ , N ^{1'} -bis-(β -cyano- ethyl) sulphanyl amide] Cobalt II	14.45	35.32	3.42	13.74	17.39	0.76	4.2 B.M.
		14.00	35.01	3.13	13.33	17.18		
XV	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-thiazolyl sulphanyl amide] Cobalt II	13.46	32.90	2.74	12.80	16.19	1.02	4.4 B.M.
		13.00	32.80	2.62	12.45	16.00		
XVI	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-pyrimidyl sulphanyl amide] Cobalt II	13.62	36.04	3.00	16.17	16.39	1.14	4.42 B.M.
		13.14	35.72	2.64	15.85	16.01		
XVII	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-(4-methyl pyrimidyl) sulphanyl amide] Cobalt II	13.19	37.60	3.35	15.67	15.87	1.08	4.5 B.M.
		12.83	37.32	3.08	15.46	15.25		
XVIII	Dichloro[N ¹ -(β -cyanoethyl) 2-(4,6-diamethyl pyrimidyl) sulphanyl amide] Cobalt II	12.78	39.06	3.68	15.19	15.38	1.34	4.4 B.M.
		12.52	38.76	3.52	15.00	15.01		

TABLE 3—FREQUENCIES AND ASSIGNMENTS FOR LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Ligands	Complexes	NH ₂ stretching in cm ⁻¹	NH ₂ bending in cm ⁻¹	C-N vibration in cm ⁻¹	C≡N frequencies in cm ⁻¹
1.	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3390,3479	1639	1274	2250
		Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3278,3328	1547	1185	2189
		Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3283,3375	1576	1205	2168
2.	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3192,3383	1585	1166	2190
		Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3226,3333	1608	1266	2228
		Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3155,3246	1525	1175	2128
3.	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	Cu(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂	3163,3295	1548	1225	2136
		Co(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂	3188,3228	1560	1189	2188
		Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂	3226,3433	1613	1250	2214
4.	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₆ O ₂ S	Cu(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂	3208,3343	1558	1190	2174
		Co(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂	3199,3375	1562	1188	2160
		Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂	3187,3368	1578	1175	2180
5.	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S	Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3385,3415	1625	1285	2260
		Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3250,3333	1565	1154	2190
		Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3234,3388	1587	1165	2174
6.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ S	Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3278,3354	1558	1197	2152
		Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3330,3475	1563	1266	2258
		Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3290,3348	1507	1130	2150
6.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ S	Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3185,3350	1525	1175	2180
		Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3225,3378	1506	1133	2165
		Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3285,3389	1642	1250	2248
6.	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ S	Co(C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3187,3268	1576	1138	2165
		Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3153,3248	1557	1188	2173
		Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ S)Cl ₂	3138,3272	1574	1154	2151

Results and Discussion

From the results of elemental analysis, the ratio of ligand with metal chlorides was found to be 1 : 1 in these complexes. They appear to be quite stable as they do not show any tendency of decomposition.

Conductance values of Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chloride complexes in nitrobenzene show that they are nonelectrolytic in nature⁹. The probability for the existence of polymeric structure due to nitrogen bridging cannot be ruled out.

Cu(II) complex :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements on the Cu(II) chloride complex of N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-pyridyl sulphanilamide, yielded the magnetic moment value of 1.82 B.M. The tetracoordinated Cu(II) complex may be either square planar or tetrahedral. The electronic spectra of the complex showed one broad band with centre at 14,586 cm⁻¹¹⁰. It indicates that magnetic and spectral properties of the complex are fairly close to that expected for square planar complex¹¹.

Similarly other Cu(II) chloride complexes showed the possibility of square planar stereochemistry.

Ni(II) complex :

The Ni(II) chloride complex of N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-pyridyl sulphanilamide yielded a magnetic moment value of 3.58 B.M.¹², showing thereby no

probability of square planar or octahedral stereochemistry. The tetrahedral structure of the complex is also supported by their intense blue colour due to the presence of an absorption band in red part of the visible region¹³. The electronic spectra shows a band at 14,500 cm⁻¹ and is assigned to the T₁(F)→T₁(P) transition (ν₃)¹⁴ and second band at 19,000 cm⁻¹. The Ni(II) complex has high intensity of absorption band and molar absorbance of ~190 at the peak of visible band¹⁵. The visible spectra of the complex resembles with other tetrahedral complexes¹⁶⁻¹⁸ so that the tetrahedral configuration is possible for N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-pyridyl sulphanilamide complex.

Similarly other Ni(II) chloride complexes of cyanoethylated sulphonamide have the same magnetic and spectral properties as that of N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-pyridyl sulphanilamide. ζ

Co(II) complex :

Co(II) chloride complex of N¹-(β-cyanoethyl)-2-pyridyl sulphanilamide is paramagnetic and tetrahedral stereochemistry around the Co(II) is possible. Magnetic moment value of the complex is 4.4 B.M. The visible spectra of the complex shows a single absorption band at 14,000 cm⁻¹ [4A₂→4T₁(P)]. The fine structure is caused by spin-orbit coupling which both splits the 4T₁(P) state and allows transitions to the neighbouring doublet states¹⁹.

Magnetic and spectral properties of other complexes are same and possibly of tetrahedral structure.

Infrared data of these complexes provide evidence for the formation of chelates as well as their adducts with nitrogen bases. The results indicate that complexes show two strong bands at the frequencies near $3000-3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which accounts for NH_2 stretching vibrations. These bands occur at frequencies about $60-100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ lower than that of the parent compound²⁰⁻²⁴. Thus the weakening of the NH_2 bands presumably due to the drainage of electrons from the nitrogen atom towards metal, indicates that these complexes exist as coordination compounds²⁵. The other band was observed at $1500-1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to bending vibration of NH_2 group. This band is also shifted to a lower frequency region on coordination with metal chloride. The C-N band is also shifted to lower frequency for account of shifting the NH_2 group.

In addition to the NH_2 bands, a $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequency is observed for each of these derivatives around $2130-2200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This represents a decrease in the $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretching frequency by some $50-100\text{ cm}^{-1}$ from that observed for ligand²⁶⁻²⁹. This decrease is about the magnitude expected if coordination occurs through the $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ triple bond and observed for the other molecules containing a CN π system involved in coordination to a metal²⁹. So it was suggested that the π -electrons of the $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ triple bond interacted with the Lewis acid.

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